

ADVANTAGES AND APPLICATION CONSTRAINTS OF PLC BASED LABORATORY TEST RIG OF MULTI-GENERATOR STEAM POWER PLANT

J. Dragosavac*, Ž. Janda*, T. Gajić*, J. Pavlović*, S. Dobričić*, B. Radojičić**,
J. V. Milanović*** and D. Arnautović *

*Electrical Engineering Institute “Nikola Tesla”, University of Belgrade, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

**Thermal Power Plants Nikola Tesla, Obrenovac, Serbia

*** The University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, UK

Abstract: The paper summarizes development of coordinated reactive power-voltage controller and PLC based laboratory test rig for multi generator thermal power plant. Theoretical background and basic practical requirements are clearly stated. Following this, several examples are presented to illustrate some of identified advantages and drawbacks of developed test rig during the laboratory testing of CQVC controller which led to improvement both test rig and CQVC controller design.

The paper presents full cycle of development of advanced controller, from laboratory test model of steam power plant to practical device. It demonstrates the necessity for and benefits of developing adequate test platform and opens the possibility of its use in further applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

The constancy of voltage is one of the major factors contributing to reliable power system operation and insuring good quality of power supply. Voltage control is closely related to reactive power control. In most cases it is fairly good assumption that real (P) and reactive (Q) power flows in transmission networks are independent since the P transfer is predominantly determined by the angle between sending and receiving end voltages while the Q transfer is predominantly determined by the difference in voltage magnitude between sending and receiving end voltages. The voltage magnitude at all buses in the network must be maintained within a certain range under varying loading conditions, ideally from no load to full load. Injection of too much Q induces high voltages in the system which may result in flashovers, equipment failures, safety issues, etc. Too little injection of Q, on the other hand, leads to low voltages in the network, danger of voltage collapse, equipment misoperation etc. In general, inadequate Q reserve may result in voltage instability and blackout.

Coordination of voltage control involves adjusting reference values of local/primary voltage and reactive power controlling equipment in the plant in a manner to achieve wider area coordination in obtaining optimal voltage profile and reactive power flows. Applied to

power system, coordination involves control according multi objective function which aggregates and weights different technical (voltage limits, voltage deviation limits, reactive power limits) and economical (voltage drop and line losses, prime mover's energy costs) aspects. However with large penetration of distributed generators into, by recent time, exclusively passive, highly meshed distribution network the voltage control strategy in distribution network is changing to a certain degree. Certainly by coordinating different voltage and reactive power control local equipment such as distributed generators, on-load tap changers and substation capacitors, smaller voltage variations, better voltage profile could be achieved in real time. Furthermore, multi-objective function which incorporates loss minimization, reactive power pricing and availability from different sources (distributed generators, switched shunt capacitors), maximization of the reactive power reserve for emergency purposes at DG by exploiting cheaper mechanically switched feeder capacitor reactive power whenever available is also achievable, by distributed smart control.

To fulfill reactive power distribution request among participating generators, coordinated Q-V controller (CQVC) needs to be installed at steam power plant (SPP) control level. This Q-V controller would coordinate the primary controllers, i.e., the AVRs, in order to provide optimal allocation of the reactive power generation among participating generators in the plant taking into account security and economical aspects. The major advantage of such CQVC is that it controls voltage of the plant busbar while maintaining equal Q distribution among participating plant generators regarding generators specific reactive capability under real operating conditions. As having very specific functions, this kind of controller is not available at open market since it is strongly related to utility structure. Each utility needs to develop it according to specific local requirements and limitations. As it controls total amount of MVar delivered by the power plant it is necessary to ensure high degree of reliability. It can be achieved by long term testing process prior commissioning.

II. BACKGROUND ON DEVELOPMENT OF COORDINATED Q-V CONTROLLER

The main purpose of a CQVC is to maintain HV busbar voltage by power plant generators in an automatic, coordinated and real-time manner.

The static performance of the CQVC should be defined according to the desired SPP busbar static Q-V characteristic, Fig. 1, and the dynamic CQVC performance should ensure non-interference among several overlapped control loops of the hierarchical voltage control system [1]. The detailed controller description is given in paper [2].

Fig. 1 Static Q-V SPP busbar characteristic imposed by CQVC: V_{HVref} is the HV busbar voltage reference value and Q_{HV} is the sum of delivered reactive powers ΣQ_i at the HV busbar, $X_{droopHV_Natural}$ is equivalent droop of HV busbars without CQVC control and $X_{droopHV}$ desired droop value with CQVC control.

The CQVC performs allocation of reactive power at the high voltage busbar (Q_{HV}) across different synchronous generators (SG) based on equal reactive margins (1st control mode) and then regulates the power plant HV busbars voltage V_{HV} by coordinating Q outputs of participating SGs (2nd control mode). CQVC responds only to slow changes (order of tens of seconds) in voltage and Q at the power plant busbars while the excitation system deals with fast changes. The regulated power plant's HV busbar's voltage is obtained as the intersection point between desired plant's busbar Q-V characteristic (thick, solid, purple line in Fig. 1) defined with HV busbar voltage reference value V_{HVref} and desired droop value HV busbar $X_{droopHV}$ and the network characteristic X_{net} (equivalent network reactance X_{net} at the point of coupling and network equivalent voltage E_{nets} , dashed line in Fig. 1). The droop in busbar characteristic is introduced in order to avoid reactive power oscillations with neighbouring plants. For desired V_{HV} and $X_{droopHV}$, the Q_{HVref} is determined based on Fig. 1 and relation (1)[2]:

$$Q_{HVref} = \left(\Sigma Q_i + \frac{V_{HVref} - V_{HV}}{X_{net}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{X_{droopHV}}{X_{net}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\Sigma Q_i = Q_{HV}$ is the sum of the individual generators reactive power outputs. At the core of the CQVC is the Q controller. It controls the total Q delivered by the plant Q_{HV} while maintaining an equal Q distribution across plant generators. The total Q reference value is at first compared with the sum of Q generated by individual SGs. Following this, the total Q error and single unit Q error with respect to demanded Q are calculated. Two main problems that the Q controller needs to resolve are Q allocation and the transfer function between controller inputs and outputs as it converts the unit's Q demand into the required change of the AVR's voltage reference value. Since the equal reactive reserve method is used, the unit's Q demand is determined based on the SG's D-diagram and the amount of actual real power generation.

To determine the necessary change in voltage reference given by (2) in order to achieve the desired Q changes, the inverse of the sensitivity matrix is used [3],

$$\left[\Delta |E_i| \right] = [S]^{-1} \left[\Delta Q_i / |E_i| \right], \quad (2)$$

where [S] is the estimated sensitivity matrix, Q_i reactive power of i -th SG and E_i is SG's Thevenin voltage. Full details about derivation of sensitivity matrix are given in [2]. The calculated changes in generator voltages are then converted into changes of AVR's voltage reference values and applied as up or down pulses for each reference voltage.

In such way a full cycle of development of advanced multi-generator SPP test rig is enlightened, from laboratory test model to practical PLC based industrial grade device. The most notable identified advantages and drawbacks of developed test rig are reported and fixed. The adequacy of the developed test rig is demonstrated by comparison of simulated and in field recorded SPP reactive power responses. All benefits of developing the adequate test platform are stressed and briefly explained.

Therefore the PLC based test rig was designed and implemented in laboratory environment.

III. DEVELOPMENT OF LABORATORY TEST RIG

For testing the designed CQVC described in previous section the laboratory test rig, SPP Simulator, is developed. The technical requirements for the SPP Simulator were defined by validation testing requirements of the coordinated Q-V controller. Consequently, the SPP Simulator transfer function is given as the relationship between a step change in the AVR's voltage reference calculated with (2) as the input, and generator reactive power as the output.

A. Modeling of generator and exciter

Since the main objective of the SPP Simulator is to reproduce reactive power flows in the power plant induced by changes in AVR's references values, the desired SPP Simulator's transfer function is the relationship between the recorded Q time response and the change in AVR's reference that induced this response. The transfer function between the AVR voltage reference and SG terminal voltage (E_q) is derived using Q response to step change in voltage reference value. The experimentally recorded reactive power step responses $q(t)$ are first normalized and then transformed from time to complex domain $q(s)$ using Laplace transform. The $q(s)$ is then multiplied by equivalent reactance, comprising the step-up transformer leakage reactance (X_b) and the network short circuit reactance, see Fig. 2

$$Eq(s) = q(s) \cdot (X_b + X_{shortcircuit}). \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2 Block diagram of QFM transfer function. The assumption that $X_b \gg X_{shortcircuit}$ is validated by field measurements. The details of approximate calculation of

voltage drop due to reactive power flow can be found in [4].

Voltage step response is further divided by Laplace transform of step change in voltage reference $\Delta u_{ref}h(t)$, in order to get the transfer function $E_q(s)/U(s)$ [5] between the terminal voltage of the generator (E_q) and the reference voltage $U(s)$ for the operating point under consideration. The obtained transfer function is of the second order as shown in (6).

$$\frac{E_q(s)}{U(s)} = q(s) \cdot X_b \cdot \frac{s}{\Delta u_{ref}} = \frac{b_1 \cdot s + b_0}{a_2 \cdot s^2 + a_1 \cdot s + a_0}. \quad (4)$$

The poles and zeros of transfer function (4) are determined based on field measurements at real power plant. Full derivation of (4) can be found in [6]. Further this generator with exciter model is transformed into discrete difference equations, suitable for numerical computing. The chosen sampling time of discrete difference process model is 0.1 s.

B. Steam power plant discrete model

The simplified equivalent single line diagram of the steam power plant “Nikola Tesla A” with associated network is shown in Fig. 3. For balanced steady state operation, generators are represented as a constant emf behind a equivalent reactance X_i ($i=1,6$), and the infinite bus as a constant voltage behind the network’s Thevenin equivalent impedance (as detailed in Fig. 3). The interconnecting impedance, X_T , are represented as purely inductive reactance, representing interconnecting transformers (T11 and T12 in Fig. 3) [7].

In order to determine voltages V_{22} and V_{40} , a set of linear algebraic equations (5), developed based on Fig. 3, is solved at each time step. The admittance matrix (\mathbf{Y}) of the system is determined by node voltage method [8], [9].

$$\mathbf{Y} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} V_{22}(k) \\ V_{40}(k) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{q1}(k)}{X_1} & \frac{E_{q2}(k)}{X_2} & \frac{E_{q3}(k)}{X_3} & \frac{E_{q4}(k)}{X_4} & \frac{E_{q5}(k)}{X_5} & \frac{E_{q6}(k)}{X_6} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{Y} is system admittance matrix, and superscript T denotes matrix transpose.

Once the HV bus voltages are calculated, the Q flow in p.u. of a single unit is derived analogous to the decoupled power flow method for transmission networks, applying the commonly used simplifications [4], [10]:

$$\frac{q_i(k)}{V_{22}(k)} = \frac{E_{qi}(k) - V_{22}(k)}{X_i}. \quad (6)$$

For the 220kV bus bar the Q flow, in p.u., of a single unit can be expressed by

$$q_i(k) = \frac{E_{qi}(k) - V_{22}(k)}{X_i} V_{22}(k), \quad i = 1,2,3,4, \quad (7)$$

The equivalent equation is used for Q flows of units connected at 400kV. Now the Q outputs of all the generators are connected together with busbars voltage values. The derived steam power plant model appropriate for sequential calculations, is presented in the form of block diagram in Fig 4. Internal coupling of Q responses of different generators is therefore clearly explained by block diagram shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Case study steam power plant equivalent scheme for designing power plant reactive power flow laboratory model

Fig. 4. Study case steam power plant derived model – SPP Simulator

C. Practical implementations

For the practical reasons of being compact and easy to handle in the laboratory, as well as at the site, the SPP-Simulator is realized on a PLC (Programmable Logic Controller) based platform [11]. Although other platforms could be used for the simulations described in the paper, the PLC platform is industrial grade equipment regarding electromagnetic interference (EMI) and other industrial application requirements on the plant site. The PLC platforms are readily available, easily configurable, physically durable and transparent to all major communication protocols and networks. Power plant owners usually insist on the use of industrial grade equipment. Also it was necessary to have the same control and measuring signals reproduced by SPP Simulator, at same voltage and current transducer levels, as in real plant. The developed PLC based simulator is shown in Fig. 5

IV. VALIDATION OF LABORATORY TEST RIG

SPP model validation [6], [11] and CQVC testing provided three groups of results. The choice of examples presented in a paper is made with aim to illustrate some of identified advantages and drawbacks of developed test rig during the laboratory testing of CQVC which led to further improvement of both test rig and CQVC controller design.

The first group of results revealed the drawbacks of designed CQVC. The second group demonstrated the

Fig. 5 Laboratory setup showing PLC based test rig and CQVC

effectiveness of test rig through matching of simulations and site responses of SPP with implemented CQVC, for disturbances which can not be tested at site. Finally, during the commissioning of CQVC, through the process of CQVC improvements and removing of identified drawbacks some shortcomings of test rig also turned out.

The design of CQVC started from the scratch. The design process included thorough review of available literature which served as basis for further theoretical development of the device as presented in section II. However, during the laboratory testing some practical drawbacks turned out. In Fig. 6 it is noticeable that the transition between two operating modes was followed by the change of SPP operating point. When working connected to network this transition is unacceptable. The CQVC algorithm is improved so that bumpless transition is achieved as recorded in Fig. 7.

The similar problem was noticed with changes of the $X_{droopHV}$. For given V_{HVref} and $X_{droopHV}$ delivered Q_{HV} is intersection point of SPP Q-V characteristic and network characteristic. With change in $X_{droopHV}$ for given V_{HVref} Q_{HV} acquires new value which moves SPP to new operating point, Fig. 8. The improvement implies recalculation of V_{HVref} whenever $X_{droopHV}$ changes in a way that Q_{HV} is kept constant, Fig. 9.

The main purpose of developing CQVC was to examine the CQVC response to large disturbances such as generator disconnection which certainly can not be tested during the commissioning. Test rig simulation of generator disconnection was validated with recorded response at the actual power plant with implemented CQVC control. Fig. 10 illustrates test rig simulation of generator disconnection and Fig. 11 validates this response by recorded response at the actual power plant with implemented CQVC control. The responses in laboratory showed that CQVC easily reallocates the occurred Q deficiency to other generators included in coordinated control. The reactive power delivered from the SPP Q_{HV} was preserved at prefault value due CQVC action (after AVR action to disturbance elapsed d in time). The record of generator disconnection at the site showed good matching of generator response received during laboratory tests and at real SPP. The event shown in Fig. 11 fully demonstrates importance of test rig development.

Finally, after the CQVC was installed at SPP although the reactive reserves were equally distributed across different types of generators the distribution of terminal voltages was not uniform, table I, [12], as expected [13]. During laboratory testing the SG's terminal voltages could not be easily observed. However these voltages have a strong influence on the actual generator reactive capability. Following this, the changes were made to CQVC algorithm and estimation of this voltage is implemented so that its influence to reactive power allocation could be taken into account, [12]. This also suggested that appropriate change should be applied to CQVC regarding future use of this test rig. Especially in the case of implementation of coordinated Q-V control to several distributed generators in wide area, additional care must be taken to the proper assessment of the influence of distributed generators to local voltage profile, especially taking into account variable distributed loads.

Fig. 6 Simulated response during the transition between 1st and 2nd control mode of the plant with implemented CQVC. A1 to A4 Q responses in MVAr. A1 (cyan solid), A2 (violet dashed), A3 (blue dotted) and A4 (red dashdotted); $V_{HV220kV}$ (black, solid)

Fig. 7 The transition between 1st and 2nd control mode with implemented CQVC recorded at site. A1 to A4 Q responses in MVAr. A1 (cyan solid), A2 (violet dashed), A3 (blue dotted) and A4 (red dashdotted); $Q_{HV220kV}$ (black, solid)

Fig. 8. Simulated response for change of $X_{droopHV}$ from 2 to 0,72%. A1 to A4 Q responses in MVAr. A1 (cyan solid), A2 (violet dashed), A3 (blue dotted) and A4 (red dashdotted); $V_{HV220kV}$ (black, solid)

Fig. 9 Units A2 to A3 Q responses in 2nd control mode A2 (violet dashed), A3 (blue dotted) and $V_{HV220kV}$ (black, solid). (P1=197MW, P2=198MW and P3=304MW).

Fig. 10 Recorded reactive power responses using test rig to simulate generator A1 disconnection. A1 to A4 Q responses in MVar. A1 (cyan solid), A2 (violet dashed), A3 (blue dotted) and A4 (red dashed); $V_{HV220kV}$ (black, solid)

Fig. 11 Recorded voltage and reactive power responses at the actual power plant with implemented CQVC following disconnection of the generator A1. Generators A1 and A4 are involved in recorded event

TABLE I CQVC WITH IMPLEMENTED ORIGINAL D DIAGRAM

	P [MW]	Q [MW]	$Q_{reserve}$ [%]	V [kV]	V [p.u.]
A1	186	103	70	14.521	0.922
A2	208	97	69	14.537	0.923
A3	283	143	71	13.615	0.9077
A4	293	148	75	13.56	0.9043

V. CONCLUSIONS

The developed PLC based laboratory test rig of multi-machine steam power plant is presented. The theoretical background and basic practical field requirements are identified and stated. Design process and device validation are clearly outlined, fully explained and supported by experimental records. Development and validation of performance of test rig are and developed test rig also gives basis for application of this concept to the distribution networks in order to obtain stable voltage map and precise and economical reactive power management. In the next step is to integrate several controllable DG units into virtual (equivalent) power plant which is capable, with the sufficient penetration rate to support MV or HV voltage like a classical power plant connected to HV grid as presented in this paper.

VI. REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHIES

Jasna Dragosavac received her Dipl.Ing. and M.Sc. degrees in Electrical Engineering from the University of Belgrade, Serbia in 1994 and 2002 respectively, her Ph.D degree from the University of Novi Sad, Serbia in 2012. Since 1995 she is with Electrical Engineering Institute "Nikola Tesla", University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia.

Žarko Janda received his Dipl. Ing., M.Sc. and PhD degrees in 1984, 1989 and 2004 respectively, from the University of Belgrade, all in Electrical Engineering. Since 1984 he is with Electrical Engineering Institute "Nikola Tesla", University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia.

Tomislav Gajić received Dipl.Ing degree in Electrical Engineering from the University of Belgrade, in 2006. Currently he is with Electrical Engineering Institute "Nikola Tesla", University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia.

Jelena Pavlović received Dipl.Ing degree in Electrical Engineering from the University of Belgrade, in 2008. Currently he is with Electrical Engineering Institute "Nikola Tesla", University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia.

Sava Dobričić received Dipl.Ing degree in Electrical Engineering from the University of Belgrade, in 1996. Currently he is with Electrical Engineering Institute "Nikola Tesla", University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia.

Bojan Radojičić received Dipl.Ing degree in Electrical Engineering from the University of Belgrade, in 2008. Currently he is with "Thermal Power Plants Nikola Tesla - A" Ltd, Obrenovac, Serbia.

Jovica V. Milanović (M'95, SM'98, F'10) Currently he is a Professor of Electrical Power Engineering and Director of External Affairs in the School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering of the University of Manchester (formerly UMIST), Manchester, UK, Visiting Professor at the University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia and Conjoint Professor at the University of Newcastle, Newcastle, Australia.

Dušan Arnautović received his Dipl. Ing., M.Sc. and PhD degrees in 1973, 1978 and 1988 respectively, from the University of Belgrade, all in Electrical Engineering. Since 1977 he is with Electrical Engineering Institute "Nikola Tesla", Belgrade, Serbia.